

RECIPE AND TECHNOLOGY OF HIGH VISCOSITY BROTH FOR THE PREPARATION OF SEMI-FINISHED PASTE SAUCES

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Abstract. Sauces are considered very important in the organization of food of the peoples of the world, they give the product a unique flavor and aroma. Proper selection of products for sauces, their processing and compatibility with food ensure good digestion. According to traditional techniques broths are prepared by grinding the bones, adding water and boiling them on low heat while removing the fat and foam. The chemical composition of the broth testifies to its high nutritional value: dry matter content 6.91%, fat 2.68%, protein 3.78%.

Keywords: sauce, broth, gluten, fat, protein, mass, consistency, amino acids.

РЕЦЕПТУРА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ВЫСОКОВЯЗКОГО БУЛЬОНА ДЛЯ ПРИГОТОВЛЕНИЯ ПОЛУФАБРИКАТОВ СОУСОВ-ПАСТ

Аннотация. Соусы считаются очень важными в организации питания народов стран мира, они придают продукту неповторимый аромат и вкус. Правильный подбор продуктов для соусов, их обработка и сочетаемость с пищей обеспечивают хорошее пищеварение. По традиционным технологиям готовят бульоны путем измельчения костей, добавления воды и варки их на слабом огне при удалении жира и пены. Химический состав бульона свидетельствует о его высокой пищевой ценности: содержание сухого вещества 6,91%, жира 2,68%, белков 3,78%.

Ключевые слова: соус, бульон, глютен, жир, белок, масса, консистенция, аминокислоты.

INTRODUCTION

It is difficult so imagine the food of the people of the countries of the world without sauces. Sauces give the product a unique aroma and taste increases the nutritional value of food. They stimulate the appetite while eating and allow the absorption of the main components of food. This figure is due to the aromatic extraction substances contained in them which use the digestive glands. The correct selection of products for sauces their processing and their compatibility with food ensure good digestion when choosing sauces, taking into account the chemical composition and nutritional value of the food, the sauce replaces the missing substances in the food. According to the classification of sauces the raw materials for their preparation are mainly broths of different bases and when the broths are boiled, nitrogenous extractive, purine bases and mineral substances are added to them increasing the pleasant taste and aroma of the broth making it suitable for preparing sauces.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

According to traditional technologies bones are chapped into 5-7 cm long pieces washed, added water and kept in low heat 5-6 hours boil while remaining oil and farm. The cooking duration of the broth is long, correspondingly energy consumption high, it is possible to extract

more bone fat into broth, the possibility of the increasing of the dry matter by 1.0-1.5 % remains studies have shut the chemical composition of the broth depends on the level of bone grinding and with an increase in the leave of bone grinding, more proteins fats and executive substances are transferred to the broth. In particular, chicken broth is distinguished not only by its nutritional value but also by it's high gluten content which positively affects the cheological properties of the broth.

G.M.Postanova and N.R.Usperskaya studies show that meant brothers are rich in mineral substances but poultry broths are superior to them in terms of organic matter.

Especially chicken broth contains a lot of gluten, which has a positive effect not only on the nutritional value, but also on the rheological properties of the broth. During cooking, additional nitrogenous substances mainly gluten are added to the broth. However, long term heat neatment leads to the decomposition of create nine and the amount of emulsified fit increase, the quality of the decreases sharply. According to the studies of K.N. Bogdonoor the broth of whole cooked poultry difference from the broth prepared from lean meat by the amount creatine - creatinine (up to 38,1-38.9%) but it is much better than it buy the amount of amino acids.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Based on the above, the relationship between the results of the interaction between the proportions of the constituent components in our house which increases as follows. In the preparation of time finished source, which increases the nutritional and biological value, the raw material is mainly broth for preparing sources. This broth is made by mixing the legs and Backbone of the bird wish water in ratio in 2:1 and boiling it 4 hours the oil formed during the boiling process is filtered, the vegetables are passed in it and the collagen mead from the bone is extracted.

Table 1

Recipe of products used for making broth (for semi-finished vegetable sauce paste)

№	Products	Consumption norms, kg	
		ugly	Net
1	Agriculture (legs, spine)	100,0	100,0
2	Onions	1,8	1,5
3	Carrot	1,8	1,2
4	Water	150,0	150,0

RESULTS

The chemical composition of semi-finished sauce broth indicates its high nutritional value.

Table 2

Comparison of the recommended semi-finished sauce broth consumption

№	Indicator name	Prepared according to No.842 broth	Under broth for semi-finished products
1	Protein content, %	0.36	3.78
2	Fat content, %	0.27	2.68
3	Dry matter content, %	1.2	6.91

It's mixed wish passeroved vegetables and added to the broth the chemical composition of the broth indicates it's high nutritional value the amount of dry matter 46.91% and the broth prepared according to the recipe N°=842 is 12% the fat content is 2.68% in the broth of semi-finished sauces and 0.275% according to the recipe N°=842 proteins are 3.78% in the broth of source semi – finished products and 0.362% according to recipe N°=842 the broth prepared for Sami – finished souce poste contain all essential amino acids. The broth is characterized by a high

content of irreplaceable proteins to total proteins in the broth is 0.362 and 0.275, respectively, this the broth protein prepared for source semi – finished products is full of value and has a clear.

DISCUSSION

Advantage over the broth prepared according to the N°=842 recipe. In terms of the amount of monounsaturated acids the broth is semi – finished products is 1.14 times better than the recipe broth. N°=842 and 6.69 times in terms of polyunsaturated acids. This broth of semi-finished products has an advantage in the composition of minerals and vitamins compared to the recipe 842 for 100bkg of semi-finished sauce paste from agricultural poultry - source broth, which is used in the production of semi-finished products product recipes and standards.

The sauce obtained for the semi-finished product of sauce-pasta has good indicators of the chemical composition of the semi-finished broth and consists of all nutritional compounds necessary for nutrition. This allows us to conclude about its high nutritional value.

CONCLUSION

Quantitative limits of the use of broth prepared for semi-finished products of source pasta come from the tasks they perform. Addition of broth at 20 percent by weight to semi-finished product of source pasta leads to thickening of the obtained product adding more than 30 percent by weight bring the semi-finished product to a liquid consistency reduces it's quality and does not allow to achieve the goal of the research. Only the quality offered for the broth of the semi-finished pasta sauce only the limit ensure the achievement of the research objective. Last than 15 percent of the weight of the flour doesn't allow binding of excess water In the broth, resulting in the semi-finished tomato sauce pasta will not have the dispersed consistently which will cause it's organoleptic indicators to be negative.

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